

Secondary mathematics teachers in England who think outside the hegemonic discourse of “ability”: Situation and horizon

Colin Jackson, Independent academic, ✉ colinfjackson@hotmail.com

Hilary Povey, Sheffield Hallam University

A neo-liberal discourse has been hegemonic in England for several decades and includes “ability” as a fundamental plank leading to and legitimising divisive and unjust grouping practices in schools. Some teachers, however, resist this discourse and believe and succeed in enacting all-attainment teaching in secondary mathematics. This paper is concerned with such teachers and, using Gadamer’s concepts of situation and horizon, offers a model for how they experience the world.

Introduction

A neo-liberal discourse of education has been hegemonic in England for several decades sweeping aside all previous assumptions (Ball, 2017) and reframing education as a consumer good rather than a moral enterprise (Povey & Adams, 2018). The discourse promulgates the idea that the unequal way that society – and schooling - is structured is natural, simply the result of free individuals and their free choices within a market. Thus, it seeks to legitimate inequality, a process that leads those at both the top and bottom of society “to see themselves as largely responsible for their own places in it” (Oakes, 1982, p. 197). The associated discourse of “ability” forms a central plank in this neo-liberal discourse, in turn legitimating divisive and unjust grouping practices in schools.

The research¹ from which this paper is drawn focused on those who challenge the practice (almost universal in secondary mathematics classrooms in England) of grouping students according to their supposed “ability”. The research participants were a small number of teachers who do not accept this “common-sense” thinking but who instead believe that all students should have access to all of the curriculum and that all students are capable of learning without limits (Hart, 2004). Using both a narrative and a thematic approach, the

¹ Much of the text here is drawn directly from Jackson, 2019. The research data and the models developed are the work of the first author; the second and subsidiary author contextualised the research and developed the paper itself.

Please cite as: Jackson, C., & Povey, H. (2021). Secondary mathematics teachers in England who think outside the hegemonic discourse of “ability”: Situation and horizon. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 2, pp. 517–525). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5414260>

research attempted to identify aspects of who these teachers are and how they find a way to resist the hegemonic education discourse. As anticipated, the teachers were committed to social justice in education; but they also shared attitudes and practices related to pedagogy. Beyond this, however, they also shared a different world view, one in which they understood their current *situation* (Gadamer, 1960/1975) as having an *horizon* (ibid.) and therefore not the only way things could be.

The neo-liberal education discourse in England

In England, the hegemonic neo-liberal discourse of education has swept aside all previous assumptions (Ball, 2017) about the purposes of education, the professionalism of teachers and what constitute moral and fitting ways of working with children and young people. A previous discourse that at least recognised the effects of systemic disadvantage has been replaced by one of blaming “failing” children, “failing” teachers and “failing” schools. Individuals are constructed as making free choices within a market, with the neo-liberal rhetoric, as always, disguising the coercion (Mattei & Salour, 2019).

An epidemic of testing beginning at age four has contributed to making children in the United Kingdom among the lowest in Europe for their declared educational well-being (UNICEF, 2013) as does the narrowness of the curriculum and teaching to the test. The explicit aim of our national compulsory curriculum is “knowing more, remembering more and being able to do more”. Ofsted is the government service which polices the education system, in particular schools’ performance in national tests (Perryman, Maguire, Braun, & Ball, 2018). As we have noted elsewhere (Povey & Angier, in press), in its *School Inspection Handbook* (Ofsted, 2021) there are 89 references to *knowledge* and 58 to *skills* but only 2 references to *thinking*, 2 to *creativity* and only 1 to *curiosity*.

Teachers too are subject to a relentless system of auditing and measuring with both teachers (Black, 2019) and students (Reay & Wiliam, 1999) being known by their “scores”. They find themselves drawn into practices which they find morally dubious (Goodley, 2019) and a performative culture pervades all their experiences in school. As one early career teacher said:

Performativity is known to all teachers whether by name or not. Its influence taints all the day-to-day activities of teachers and subconsciously affects the way they view their role. (Povey & Adams, 2017, p. 58)

The effect is to erode their sense of independence and moral authority and to challenge their collective professional identities (Povey & Adams, 2017). Many teachers² are attempting to “restory” themselves (Stronach et al., 2002, p. 130); there is indeed a battle over the teacher’s soul (Ball, 2003).

² Personal experience and anecdotes from a wide range of sources suggest that this restorying has become much more prevalent during the COVID-19 pandemic, laying bare as it has both the inequalities and injustices of the current situation and the capabilities and professionalism of education workers.

Social justice, “ability” thinking and grouping practices

An essential plank of the neo-liberal educational discourse in England is the notion of “ability”. The term is very seldom interrogated; it is simply accepted as unchallengeable “common-sense” that children come to school with different “abilities” which are measurable and more or less fixed. Thus school-based discussions of “ability” often take for granted:

a series of assumptions that, while exerting a considerable influence on the life in school, are rarely voiced in an explicit or systematic way. (Gillborn & Youdell, 2000, p. 52)

In England it is now rare to find a secondary school where the pupils are not in “ability” groupings for mathematics (Francis et al., 2017). In addition, there is evidence that children in primary schools are increasingly being put into “ability” groupings (Hallam, Ireson and Davies, 2004; Drummond and Yarker, 2013). This is despite the very substantial research evidence showing that this is undesirable for students and unfair and unjust in its outcomes.

Allocating students to “ability” groups is a social justice issue, always disadvantaging somebody, and in England, amongst others, disadvantaging working-class children (Cahan, Linchevski, Ygra, and Danziger, 1996, p. 30) and some groups of black and Asian heritage students (Gillborn & Youdell, 2000). Research on “ability” grouping indicates that it has little, if any effect, on attainment averaged overall but has long term detrimental effects in terms of personal and social outcomes (Nunes, Bryant, Sylva, & Barros, 2009; Boaler, 2005). Indeed the social effects of “ability” grouping are found to be overwhelmingly negative (Boaler, 1997; Cahan et al., 1996; Marks, 2013). The practice is damaging to children’s development with the long-term effect, continuing into adulthood, of resulting in more limited horizons, stunted intellectual growth and a lower self-evaluation of one’s worth and the possibilities available (Boaler, 2005; Cahan et al., 1996).

Methodology, methods and analysis

The research project was framed within critical theory, actively acknowledging that knowledge and discourse are not neutral but are socially constructed, and with the intention of being “deliberately political” (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2007, p. 26). It was conceived as an attempt “to free academic work from capitalistic domination and to help schools and other institutions to become places where people might be socially empowered rather than subjugated” (Tedlock, 2007, p. 153), to act as an emancipatory force in the world. Both authors are committed to pursuing social justice aims in and through mathematics education and the research was conducted from that declared standpoint.

Lather (1991) believes that for critical theory research to be taken seriously it must be trustworthy and needs to display catalytic validity: catalytic validity enables the participants to understand the reality of their lived existence and empowers them to do something about it. There is evidence that, for at least some of the participants, enhanced understanding and commitment to (continuing) action resulted from participation. In addition, we wanted the research to impact on the world more widely. So the key questions for us are: is the research credible? and does it have the power to act on the world?

Adopting critical theory had implications for the research design: “a critical epistemology assumes that valid knowledge is obtained in part through shared understandings, reflexivity, sensitivity to insiders” (Jungck, 1996, p. 624). Thus, the participants identified were six teachers committed to teaching their students in all-attainment groups. The intention was to uncover their attributes, intentions, outlooks and perceptions of all-attainment teaching.

Semi-structured in-depth interviews were conducted (with some ethnographic details collected to support these). Interviews as a research method fit well with critical research as they are adaptable; there are opportunities for personalisation and construction of knowledge through shared meaning. The interview transcripts and individual portraits constructed from them were returned to the participants for their comments. Of the six participants, five replied. Three of those suggested minor alterations, the other two accepting the portrait without asking for any changes. Indeed, one of the participants replied:

I’ve just read your interview notes and they are extremely accurate. I had no idea I’d revealed so much! (Sarah, email correspondence)

All of these participants reported that the transcripts and the portraits were an accurate reflection of what they had said. These responses suggest that the data are reliable and offer (internal) participant validity (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2007).

Constructing the narratives was the initial approach to data analysis. Some common patterns of response emerged and so an inductive thematic analysis was also undertaken. The analysis was extended, thorough and systematic (see Jackson, 2019, pp. 74–79 for details). The findings from this analysis produced three overarching categories which were:

- the teachers – what sustains them
- introducing, developing and maintaining all-attainment teaching while convincing others
- how the teachers make all-attainment work in the classroom.

Each of these had a number of themes and subthemes (Jackson, 2019, pp. 74–79). A final stage in the analysis involved stepping back from the details of these analyses and, drawing at this stage on Gadamer (1960/1975), coming to an understanding of how these teachers see themselves in relation to the world. It is this which is the subject of this paper.

Situation and horizon and English secondary mathematics teachers

After the thematic analysis was complete, it became apparent that, cross-cutting the themes, there was something else: there was a sense that how these teachers *were in the world*, their sense of themselves in relation to the world, what they took as being self-evident or given, was somewhat different from the current lifeworld of most secondary mathematics teachers in England. Drawing on understandings from Habermas (1987), we see that lifeworlds – those “panoramic constellation of contexts, realities and understandings” (Dufays et al., 2020, p. 3) – can become colonised by economic and political interference, creating “a growing sense of powerlessness felt by individuals in relation to their ability to self-determine their lives” (p. 2), including their working lives, and the erosion of shared experience within a community.

Secondary mathematics teachers in England who think outside the hegemonic discourse

Figure 1: The teachers, the situation and beyond the horizon. (Jackson, 2019, p. 143)

In trying to understand this difference better, it has been useful to draw on the work of Hans-Georg Gadamer (1960/1975), in particular his two interlinked concepts of *situation* and *horizon*:

We define the concept of “situation” by saying that it represents a standpoint that limits the possibility of vision. Hence an essential part of the concept of situation is the concept of “horizon”. The horizon is the range of vision that includes everything that can be seen from a particular vantage point ... A person who has no horizon is a man (*sic*) who does not see far enough and hence overvalues what is nearest to him. (1960/1975, p. 269).

For Gadamer our understandings always take place in a particular situation, one in which we are entangled, one dependent on our history. This situation is the standpoint from which we experience the world, our vantage point. Our vision, then, is inevitably limited and has an horizon. However, our relationship with the horizon is not predetermined and varies between different people in the same situation. It is possible to experience our situation as *all that there is and all that there could be*. The way things are is inevitable and how things must be: there is no possible beyond.

In the context which we are considering, the current dominant educational discourse and the educational world that it produces are the situation for all teachers. Included in this is the ideological commitment to “ability” thinking and we see that, for many secondary mathematics teachers, the putative differences in something innate and relatively unchangeable – the ability to succeed in mathematics – is an unquestioned “truth” (Marks, 2013; Gillborn & Youdell, 2000). The landscape is horizonless and what is currently inhabited is all that there is and all that there could be.

But for the participants in the research study, in the same situation, they can see an horizon to the current landscape.

To have an horizon means not to be limited to what is nearest, but to be able to see beyond it. A person who has an horizon knows the relative significance of everything within this horizon, as near or far, great or small. (Gadamer, 1960/1975, p. 269).

So they both see the situation they are in more clearly and can also envisage that things can be different from how they are proposed in and produced by the hegemonic educational discourse.

Figure 1 represents how the participating teachers see and understand the framework within which they are operating. They engage critically with and question the world within which they are situated. They reject the limitations on their students imposed by the hegemonic common-sense of fixed “ability” thinking (Gillborn and Youdell, 2000; Archer et al., 2017). Because they see the horizon to this thinking, they can see the opportunities beyond it.

In doing so they are open to thinking about the possibilities from both historical and current day perspectives. They are able to use these resources for communicative action (Habermas, 1987) to resist colonisation of their lifeworlds and to redefine the institutional arrangements imposed upon them (Dufays et al., 2020; Stronach et al., 2002). They are able to consider possibilities that have arisen in the recent past in England; for example, in the

Secondary mathematics teachers in England who think outside the hegemonic discourse

late seventies/early eighties when all-attainment existed in around a fifth of secondary mathematics lessons (Ruthven, 1987). They can examine the practices in other curriculum areas in schools in England where all-attainment still exists today to a much greater extent than in mathematics (Archer et al., 2017). They can look for schools where all-attainment in mathematics is still practised – there are still a few. They can look at other countries and see that all-attainment may not just be a practice but a legal requirement (Gates & Noyes, 2021, p. 48); for example, it is illegal to put students into “ability” groups in Sweden due to issues of equality (Boaler, 2005). These teachers question the *status quo*, knowing that there are alternatives that serve all students better; they imagine what could be and attempt to enact it in their teaching, so things are better for all of their students, not just a select few.

In addition, all-attainment for these teachers is not only about the students’ experience of learning mathematics important as that is for them: they are also concerned with the students’ future life chances. Unsurprisingly, for most of these teachers the field of social justice impinges on the field of mathematics education informing their decisions. Bob expresses this quite succinctly:

My reasons for mixed-attainment are the philosophical reasons of social justice and giving everyone a chance and putting the responsibility on the students, giving them the opportunity to show what they can do rather than me say ‘This is what you can do and bad luck whether you think you can do anything else, you’re not going to get the chance’.
[Bob, transcript]

These teachers try to build an interdependent community (Healy, 2019) of independent learners and to enable the students to develop as critical thinkers so that they are not limited by their situation and they too develop an horizon, so they too can see beyond their current situation.

The more you get people to (question the world), the less likely they are to then simply accept things that are handed down from above. They feel an equality. Because they have this richness and ability to [think] if I don’t know it yet, I’m open to learning and I want to learn it, and I’m capable of thinking, capable of learning it, and therefore I won’t simply have to bow down and accept and [not] question authority or expertise, I can challenge, question. You might tell me something, you might know more [than me] about this but I’m perfectly capable of thinking about that, if necessary going away and learning some more about it, and questioning. (Pete, interview transcript)

They believe that unless the students develop their critical thinking capacity, they cannot fully exercise their right to engage critically with and question the reasons why society and, indeed, schools are the way they are and to contribute to a more socially just world.

Conclusion

In this paper we have argued that teachers in England who are able to resist having their educational thinking colonised by the hegemonic neo-liberal discourse reject “ability” thinking and the associated practices of grouping students. Further, we have argued that one way of understanding these teachers is by considering their relationship to the *situation* in

which they find themselves. Specifically, we have drawn on Gadamer's notion of *horizon* to model how they are in the world and to draw attention to how what lies beyond the horizon can support more radical thinking. In turn this supports the teachers in working towards a more just mathematics education in schools.

References

- Archer, L., Francis, B., Miller, S., Taylor, B., Tereshchenko, A., Mazenod, A., . . . Travers, M. (2018). *The symbolic violence of setting: A Bourdieusian analysis of mixed methods data on secondary students' views about setting*. Abingdon: Carfax Publishing, Taylor & Francis. <https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3321>
- Ball, S. (2003). The teacher's soul and the terrors of performativity. *Journal of Education Policy*, 18(2), 215–228.
- Ball, S. (2017). *The education debate* (3rd ed.). Bristol: Policy Press.
- Black, B. (2019). It's not just about workload: A case study into the retention of Heads of Mathematics (HoMs) in secondary schools in Northern England (Doctoral dissertation). University of Sheffield, Sheffield, United Kingdom.
- Boaler, J. (2005). The “psychological prisons” from which they never escaped: The role of ability grouping in reproducing social class inequalities. *FORUM*, 47(2), 135–144. <https://doi.org/10.2304/forum.2005.47.2.2>
- Boaler, J. (1997). *Experiencing school mathematics: Teaching styles, sex and setting*. Buckingham: Open University Press.
- Cahan, S., Linchevski, L., Ygra, N., & Danziger, I. (1996). The cumulative effect of ability grouping on mathematical achievement: A longitudinal perspective. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 22(1), 29–40.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2007). *Research methods in education* (6th ed.). London: Taylor & Francis.
- Drummond, M. J., & Yarker, P. (2013). Editorial. The enduring problem of fixed ability: But is a new conversation beginning? *Forum*, 55(1), 3–7. <https://doi.org/10.2304/forum.2013.55.1.3>
- Dufays, F., O'Shea, N., Huybrechts, B., & Nelson, T. (2020). Resisting colonization: Worker cooperatives' conceptualization and behaviour in a Habermasian perspective. *Work, Employment and Society*, 34(6), 965–984.
- Francis, B., Archer, L., Hodgen, J., Pepper, D., Taylor, B., & Travers, M. (2017). Exploring the relative lack of impact of research on ‘ability grouping’ in England: A discourse analytic account. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 47(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764X.2015.1093095>
- Gadamer, H. (1975). *Truth and method*. London: Sheed and Ward. (Original work published 1960)
- Gates, P., & Noyes, A. (2021). School mathematics as social classification. In G. Ineson & H. Povey. (Eds.), *Debates in mathematics education* (pp. 43–54). London: Routledge.
- Gillborn, D., & Youdell, D. (2000). *Rationing education: Policy, practice, reform, and equity*. Buckingham: Open University Press.
- Goodley, C. (2019). Beyond the terrors of performativity: teachers developing at the interface (Doctoral dissertation). Manchester Metropolitan University, Manchester, United Kingdom.
- Habermas J. (1987). *Theory of communicative action: Lifeworld and system: A critique of functionalist reason*. Boston: Beacon Press.

Secondary mathematics teachers in England who think outside the hegemonic discourse

- Hallam, S., Ireson, J., & Davies, J. (2004). Grouping practices in the primary school: What influences change? *British Educational Research Journal*, 30(1), 117–140.
- Hart, S. (2004). *Learning without limits*. Maidenhead: Open University Press.
- Healy, L. (2019). Critical mathematics teaching for global citizenship: Difficulties and dilemmas (Unpublished seminar contribution). Sheffield Hallam University, Sheffield, United Kingdom.
- Jackson, C. (2019). All-attainment secondary mathematics teaching in England: How some teachers make it work (Doctoral dissertation). Sheffield Hallam University, Sheffield, United Kingdom. <http://shura.shu.ac.uk/26437>
- Jungck, S. (1996). *Critical ethnography in educational research: A theoretical and practical guide*. Arlington, VA: American Anthropological Association.
- Lather, P. A. (1991). *Getting smart: Feminist research and pedagogy with/in the postmodern*. New York: Routledge.
- Marks, R. (2013). “The blue table means you don’t have a clue”: The persistence of fixed-ability thinking and practices in primary mathematics in English schools. *Forum for Promoting 3-19 Comprehensive Education*, 55(1), 31–44.
- Mattei, C., & Salour, S. (2019, April 2). Austerity is a political choice, not an economic necessity. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2019/sep/02/austerity-is-a-political-choice-not-an-economic-necessity>
- Nunes, T., Bryant, P., Sylva, K., & Barros, R. (2009). *Development of maths capabilities and confidence in primary school*. (No. DCSF-RR118). London: Department for Children, Schools and Families.
- Oakes, J. (1982). Classroom social relationships: Exploring the Bowles and Gintis hypotheses. *Sociology of Education*, 55(4), 197–212. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2112672>
- Ofsted. (2021). School inspection handbook. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/school-inspection-handbook-eif>
- Perryman, J., Maguire, M., Braun, A., & Ball, S. (2018). Surveillance, governmentality and moving the goalposts: The influence of OfSTED on the work of schools in a post-panoptic era. *British Journal of Educational Studies*, 66(2), 145–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071005.2017.1372560>
- Povey, H. & Angier, C. (in press). Against ‘progress’. *Forum*, 63(2).
- Povey, H., & Adams, G. (2018). Possibilities for mathematics education? Aphoristic fragments from the past. *The Mathematics Enthusiast*, 15(1), 159–177. <https://scholarworks.umt.edu/tme/vol15/iss1/10>
- Povey, H., & Adams, G. with Everley, R. (2017) “Its influence taints all”: Urban mathematics teachers resisting performativity through engagement with the past. *Journal for Urban Mathematics Education*, 10(2), 52–65. <https://journals.tdl.org/jume/index.php/JUME/article/view/311/219>
- Reay, D., & Wiliam, D. (1999). ‘I’ll be a nothing’: Structure, agency and the construction of identity through assessment. *British Educational Research Journal*, 25(3), 343–354.
- Ruthven, K. (1987). Ability stereotyping in mathematics. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 18(3), 243–253.
- Stronach, I., Corbin, B., McNamara, O., Stark, S., & Warne, T. (2002). Towards an uncertain politics of professionalism: Teacher and nurse identities in flux. *Journal of Education Policy*, 17(1), 109–138.
- Tedlock, B. (2007). The observation of participation and the emergence of public ethnography. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.). *Strategies of qualitative inquiry* (pp. 151–172). London: Sage.
- UNICEF (2013). The well-being of children: Short version of the Report for Young People in the UK. <https://www.unicef.org.uk/publications/report-card-11-child-wellbeing-what-do-you-think>